

THE CORRELATION BETWEEN SELF-CONCEPT AND SELF-ESTEEM WITH THE LIFESTYLE OF KOREAN-POP CULTURE STUDENT FANS AT SMAN 7 BEKASI, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

The advancement of technology nowadays has also impacted the advancement of global information, including the globalization of culture that is currently developing around the world, one of the cultures impacted by this is Korean pop culture trends. The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between the self-concept and self-esteem with the lifestyle of Korean pop culture student fans at SMAN 7 Bekasi. Fifty participants were chosen to participate in this study, using the census sample method. While the validity and reliability of the study are tested with SPSS version 17.00 for Windows. The validity of self-concept variable is at the range of 0,825 – 0,999, while the validity of the self-esteem variable is 0,631 – 0,892. The lifestyle variable validity is 0, 505 – 0, 716. The result of *bivariate correlation* data analysis obtained the r of 0.450, meaning that there is a positive correlation between the self-concept and lifestyle variables. The r score for data analysing process shows the number of 0, 488 meaning that there are positive results of data analysis obtained an r value of 0.488 which means there is a positive correlation between the self-esteem and lifestyle variables. Using the *multivariate correlation*, the r score is shown to be 0, 491, meaning that there is positive correlation between the self-concept and self-esteem variables with the lifestyle variable. According to these results, we can conclude that there is positive relationship between the self-concept and self-esteem variables with the lifestyle applied by the students who are fa analysis obtained R of 0.491 means that there is a positive direction relationship between self-concept and self-esteem with lifestyle. Based on the results of the above analysis it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between self-concept and self-esteem with the lifestyle of Korean-pop culture student fans at SMAN 7 Bekasi.

Keywords: self-concept, self-esteem, lifestyle

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1. Introduction

The current era of globalization has penetrated to almost all corners of the world without exception of Indonesia as a developing country. The advancement of technology has resulted in the globalization of information, fashion trends, entertainment and the proliferation of various electronic media devices and the exposure of varied cultures in the world are spread throughout the world. This relates to the globalization of culture in which this statement can be said to be a factor of the spread of certain values and cultures from a country to the whole world so that it becomes a *world culture*. One culture that is significantly influencing other countries nowadays is Korean pop culture or better known as Kpop / *Hallyu Wave* / *Korean Wave* (<http://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hallyu>).

The *Hallyu* phenomenon, or *Korean Wave* or Korean Fever, refers to the popularity of Korean culture abroad and offers the latest Korean entertainment which includes films, dramas, pop music, animations, *games* and the like (www.wikipedia.org/korean-wave). The spread of Korean pop culture is also supported by various mass media that actively introduces the culture and one of the intensive media in spreading this culture is television. Almost every day people can watch programs related to Korean pop culture on almost all television stations such as TOP K-POP music shows on Ochannel station, *Extra Popcorn* on Bchannel and Korean drama shows on Indosiar.

Korean pop culture fans are generally dominated by young women, even though a number of boys also adore the culture of the home country of *ginseng* as well. The developing phenomenon of Korean pop culture, consciously or not, has created lifestyle among its fans, starting from haircuts, the way the idols dress, accessories, their use of technology, and even Korean-concept cafes is considered as one indicator how spreading the Korean-pop culture already is in Indonesia.

Lifestyle itself is defined by Plummer (in Olivia M. Kaparang, 2013: 3) is a way of life identified by how individuals spend their time (activities), what individuals consider important in their lives (interests), and what individuals think about the world around them. As Branden (2001: 11) revealed, a person's lifestyle is influenced by the self-concept that an individual has. Meanwhile, the definition of self-concept is more about how individuals see what and who they are inside, whether they realize it or not; individuals examine their own strengths and weaknesses.

According to Loudon and Bitta (in Martha, Sri Hartati, & Imam Setyawan, 2010: 5) one of the factors that play an important role in determining one's lifestyle is personality, through the ability to respect others and themselves, these conditions are related to individual's self-esteem. Tambunan (2001: 1) stated that self-esteem implies an outcome of one's judgment about him/herself, expressed in attitudes that can be positive and negative. Based on the author's observations and conversations with the students for this study, they often take their time and spend their money to meet this kind of lifestyle that is line with the development of Korean pop culture.

Therefore, the authors are interested in conducting research with the title of "The relationship between self-concept and self-esteem with the lifestyle of Korean-pop culture student fans at SMAN 7 Bekasi".

2. Literature Review

2.1 Lifestyle

There are various definitions to explain the notion of lifestyle. According to Engel, Blackwell and Miniard (1995: 449), lifestyle is a pattern where a person lives in spending his time and money. Loudon & Della Bitta (1993: 61) defined lifestyle as a way of someone spending their time in an activity, interest, and important things around and to them, their opinions and views about themselves and the world around them. According to Mowen (1995:236) lifestyle is a relationship of how someone lives, spend their money, and allocates their time. Through the concept of lifestyle, Alfred Adler (in Hall & Lindzey, 2005: 249) explained the uniqueness of a person. Lifestyle is a unique way of each person in achieving specific goals that have been determined in a particular living environment, where the person is located. The factors that affect lifestyle according to Armstrong (in Nugraheni, 2003: 3) can be grouped into external factors such as 1) Reference groups, 2) Family, 3) Social class, 4) Social systems, and 5) Culture. While internal factors are 1) Attitude, 2) Experience and observation, 3) Personality, 4) Self-concept, 5) Motives and 6) Perception. Chaney (in Idi Subandy, 1997: 23) revealed that there are several forms of lifestyle, including: lifestyle industries, lifestyle advertisements, *public relations* and journalism, independent lifestyle, and hedonic lifestyle.

The measurement of lifestyle is stated in statements in AIO (*Activities, Interest, Opinion*) and the dimensions of this are described by Plummer (in Loudon & Della Bitta, 1993: 61) as follows: 1) *Activities* included in them are works, hobbies, social activities, holidays, entertainments, clubs memberships, communities, shopping and sports, 2) *Interests* that include family, home, work, communities, recreations, clothings, foods, media and achievements 3) *Opinion* included self, social, political, business, economic, education, product, future, and cultural issues. Based on the definitions above, we can conclude that lifestyle is a pattern or the way someone lives their lives, use time and money, things that matter and interesting, and things they constantly think of themselves and the world around them.

2.2 Self Concept

The self-concept is a depiction a person has about him/herself, which is formed by experiences gained from interactions with the environment (Hendriati, 2009: 138). Fitts (in Hendriati, 2009: 138) argues that self-concept is an important aspect in a person, because one's self-concept is a *frame of reference* in interacting with the environment. Hurlock (2000: 58) argues that self-concept is a picture that people have about themselves. This concept is a combination of beliefs that people have about themselves (physical, psychological, social and emotional characteristics, aspirations and achievements). Fitts

(Hendriati, 2009: 139) divides self-concept into two principle dimensions: 1) Internal dimensions, consist of self-identity, self-behavior, and self-assessor; 2) External dimensions consist of physical self, moral-ethical-self, personal-self, family-self, and social-self.

Rosenberg (Burns, 1993: 73) describes some combinations that are constructed to become a component of self-concept, they are self-image, the affective intensity, and behavioral predispositions. Calhoun & Acocella (in Sapti Wulansari, 2010: 7) stated that individuals who own negative self-concept will have negative judgment about themselves as they compare themselves as less than anybody else. On the other side, individuals who own positive self-concept tend to judge themselves as positive so they can accept themselves the way they are. Based on these descriptions about self-concept, it can be concluded that self-concept is how individuals view and describe themselves in general, and their perception about how they figure, assess themselves and their abilities, and how they think about themselves.

2.3 Self-Esteem

In our common talks, sometimes we refer to self-esteem as a border of how far individuals give appreciation, judgment, and approval on and how they like themselves. One of the important aspects in forming an individual's personality is knowing the self-esteem first. Santrock (2002:356) expressed that self-esteem is a thorough evaluative dimension of self. Self-esteem is also sometimes referred to self-value or self-image. According to Branden (1999: 5), self-esteem is a combination of self-confidence and self-respect. Self-esteem is an ability to tackle challenges in life and the rights to feel joy. Moreover, Branden added that self-esteem is how individuals think and feel about themselves, not what others' think and feel about someone else's description of them. Self-esteem is varied in each of individuals, some has high self-esteem, some has low self-esteem. The variations of self-esteem are related to its formation mechanism. Coopersmith (in Herz, 1999: 742) stated that the forming of self-esteem is affected by four aspects, they are *being able*, *being important*, *being success*, and *being worth*. According to Branden (1995: 27), self-esteem has two correlating components: self-efficacy and self-respect. From these explanations, we can conclude that self-esteem is an individual personal evaluation about their ability, importance, success, and worth expressed through their attitudes towards themselves. This evaluation about self includes positive and negative statements to value themselves.

2.4 The correlation between self-concept and self-esteem with lifestyle

The stronger the influence of globalization, the more it is to impact the society, these days. The era of modernization and technological advancements also make changes that can affect individual behavior. One of the evident changes is the change of cultural values, it is seen from the rise of Korean-pop culture lifestyle being followed by some teenagers. Hurlock (1990:207) noted that adolescents have doubts about their role that they have to carry out in this world. At this time a teenager is no longer a child, but also not yet an adult. This unclear adolescent status gives them an opportunity to explore and try

various lifestyles and determine the patterns of behavior, values and traits that will be suitable for them. On these days, with the strong current of globalization and modernization, there comes a shifting in values applied in the society. Branden (2001: 11) revealed that there are several factors that influence attitudes toward lifestyle, one of which is self-concept. The self-concept is a description of what and who a person is, the way they describe their strengths and weaknesses, whether they are aware of it or not. Self-concept is closely related to attitude, because self-concept affects all choices and decisions an individual makes, the self-concept will also create variety of lifestyles of each individual. Adolescents with negative or unfavorable self-concepts will often feel unsatisfied with themselves and will be very easily influenced by their surroundings because they are less able to accept themselves, have low self-esteem and are easily influenced by external persuasions. On the contrary, if a teenager has a good or positive self-concept, then the teenager will be able to have a better self-acceptance, also will be able to like himself more and live more effectively so that the teenager can avoid all kinds of bad influences around them. Later on, the factors that influence the forming of lifestyle are cultures, group of reference, social status, family, personality, motivation, attitude and perception. One factor that plays an important role in determining one's lifestyle is personality, through the ability to respect others and themselves, according to Loudon and Bitta, the condition is related to adolescent's self-esteem (in Martha, Sri Hartati, Imam Setyawan, 2010: 5).

According to Coopersmith (in Martha, Sri Hartati, Imam Setyawan, 2010: 5) self-esteem is a personal evaluation by an individual regarding feelings of worth or meaning in their attitudes toward oneself. Self-esteem plays an important role in the process of finding self-identity in adolescence, because it can help the teenagers recognize themselves, so that it can help increase self-confidence and will facilitate adolescents in making adjustments. Teenagers with low self-esteem have a lack of self-confidence and worry that their statements and opinions will not be liked by other individuals, live in the shadow of social groups, and participate less in the social environment. Indications of teens who have high self-esteem: they will be active and comfortable with their social environment. Teenagers with high self-esteem will display a behavior that can lead to the achievement of success in relationships, so they will be able to adapt to the influence of lifestyle. Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that an individual's lifestyle is inseparable from the self-concept and the need for self-esteem, this is due to the demands of the environment and the desire of individuals to be accepted or recognized by the environment. This explanation also reveals about the correlation of self-concept and self-esteem with the choice of lifestyle within adolescent girls who are fans of Korean pop culture. Lifestyle behavior in adolescents is carried out in order to support social relations with the environment related to self-concept and self-esteem.

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Design

This study is conducted using quantitative research method, with census sampling method to collect data. Then the analysis is processed using SPSS version 17.00 for Windows with *multivariate correlation*.

3.2 Participants

The population chosen for the study is the students of SMAN 7 Bekasi with the characteristics of age is around 15-18 years and are fans of Korean-pop culture as many as 50 students.

3.3 Materials

Likert scale is used to collect the data for the study with three scales: the lifestyle scale, self-concept scale, and self-esteem scale. Lifestyle scales are arranged based on the dimensions of Plummer (in Loudon & Bitta, 1993: 61) which consists of dimensions of activity, interest, and opinion. Self-concept scale is compiled based on the dimensions of self-concept constructed by Fitts (Hendriati, 2009: 139), consisting of internal dimensions and external dimensions. While Branden's self-esteem scale is constructed based on the self-esteem components theorized by him, there are self-efficacy and self-respect. For hypothesis testing, the researchers use *Bivariate Correlation* and *Multivariate Correlation* methods with SPSS version 17.00 for Windows.

4. Result and Discussion

As the result, the r value obtained is 0,450, meaning that there is a correlation between self-concept with lifestyle of students who are fans of Korean-pop culture at SMAN 7 Bekasi. The r value of 0,488 for self-esteem and lifestyle shows that there is a correlation between self-esteem and lifestyle of students who are fans of Korean-pop culture at SMAN 7 Bekasi. Meanwhile, the correlation between self-concept and self-esteem and lifestyle among students who are fans of Korean-pop culture is shown by the r value that is 0,491. The determinant coefficient or *R Square* is of 0,241% shows that the self-concept and self-esteem contributes 24,1% of lifestyle variable. The self-concept variable in this study contributes 20,3% on lifestyle variable and self-esteem 3,8%. Other than those, 75,9% is contributed by other factors not examined.

Based on the analysis results of the study, the correlation coefficient r value obtained is 0.450, this means that there is a relationship between self-concept and lifestyle. Thus, the correlation test result indicates that there is a positive directional relationship between self-concept and the lifestyle of Korean-pop culture fans in students at SMAN 7 Bekasi. That is, the more positive the self-concept, the higher the lifestyle of students of Korean pop culture fans at SMAN 7 Bekasi. This is supported by Fuhrmann's statement (in Prasetyo Budi Widodo, 2006: 3) that self-concept is a basic concept about oneself,

personal thoughts and opinions, awareness of what and who an individual is, and how it compares between an individual and others. Things included in this self-perception are physical, sexual, cognitive, moral, occupational or anything that has been done using skills, roles, competencies, appearance, motivation, goals or emotions.

According to the data analysis result, the correlation coefficient r value obtained is 0.488, this means that there is a relationship between self-esteem and lifestyle. Thus, the results of the correlation test indicate a positive directional relationship between self-esteem and lifestyle in students of Korean pop culture fans at SMAN 7 Bekasi. That is, the more positive the self-esteem, the higher the lifestyle of students who are fans of Korean-pop culture at SMA Negeri 7 Bekasi. This result is supported by the statement of Tambunan (2001: 1) that self-esteem implies an individual evaluation of self which is expressed in attitudes that can be both positive and negative. How individuals evaluate themselves will influence behavior in one's daily life.

While the correlation coefficient r value is 0.491, meaning that there is a relationship between self-concept and self-esteem and lifestyle in Korean-pop culture fan students at SMAN 7 Bekasi. Thus, the results of the multivariate correlation test describe a positive directional relationship between self-concept and self-esteem and lifestyle in Korean-pop culture fan students at SMAN 7 Bekasi. This is consistent with the opinion of Fitts (in Hendriati, 2009: 138) who argued that the self-concept is an important aspect in a person, because one's self-concept is a *frame of reference* in interacting with the environment.

Based on the categorization calculation, lifestyle is at a high categorization with a mean finding of 145.90, categorization for self-concept is at a high category with a mean finding of 102.34 and for self-esteem is at a high category with a mean finding of 111.38. The results of this study indicate that if self-concept and self-esteem are high, the higher a person's lifestyle becomes.

5. Conclusion

From this study, we can conclude that there is a positive directional relationship between self-concept and self-esteem and lifestyle of students who are fans of Korean-pop culture at SMAN 7 Bekasi. The more positive the self-concept and self-esteem, the higher the lifestyle will become.

6. Recommendations

The researchers may suggest for the further studies about this topic with the same title but different and broader scope of subject, for examples in Jabodetabek (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, Bekasi) area or national scope, with the consideration of the high interest of Korean-pop culture among Indonesian teenagers and even adults.

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